

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF SERVICE QUALITY, HEALTH CONSCIOUSNESS, AND PERCEIVED VALUE TO IMPROVE REVISIT INTENTION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15852877>

Published Date: 10-July-2025

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to provide an overview of service quality, health consciousness, perceived value, and revisit intention as a basis for compiling a model for increasing revisit intention. This study is a descriptive qualitative study. Data collection was carried out through questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive analysis. The results showed that respondents' perceptions of service quality at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali were in the good category; health consciousness was in the high category; perceived value was in the high category; and revisit intention was also relatively high. These conditions can be used to compile a model for increasing revisit intention to ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali.

Keywords: service quality, health conscious, perceived value, intention to revisit.

1. INTRODUCTION

When tourists want to travel to a destination, service quality is an important thing to consider. In terms of ethnowellness tourism, the differences in each region offer various services based on the local wisdom of each region. The quality of service offered by a destination can influence tourists' intention to revisit the destination, but other studies show the opposite, that service quality is not necessarily able to increase tourists' intention to revisit a destination (Abdulla et al. 2019; An et al., 2019; Khoo, 2020). In addition to being able to increase the intention to revisit, service quality can also create perceived value (Keshavarz & Jamshidi, 2018; Ozkan et al., 2019; Bashir et al., 2020). In addition to service quality, the intention to revisit an ethnowellness tourism destination is also influenced by a tourist's health consciousness.

Ethnowellness tourism cannot be separated from the health awareness of tourists. Tourists who want to travel, especially wellness tourism, have the characteristic of being people who are health conscious. Hao & Chenyue (2021) stated that health awareness affects consumption intention. When tourists have high health awareness, it will increase their intention to revisit a tourist destination (Lee, 2017; Han et al., 2020; Sukaatmadja et al., 2022). In addition, consumer behavior changes when their health awareness preferences change according to changes in their lives. If consumers are willing to pay or are willing to change their consumption, it can be indicated that they feel some benefits (Anannukul & Yoopecth, 2022). This health awareness also has an influence on perceived value (Ren et al., 2017). Perceived value is the perception of benefits felt by tourists which can affect their intention to revisit. Several studies have shown that the higher the perceived value, the more tourists' intention to revisit (Abbasi et al., 2021). Based on the existing background, this study examines service quality, health consciousness, perceived value, and intention to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali so that it can be used as a basis for developing a strategy model to increase intention to revisit.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Service Quality

In today's socio-economic environment, the service sector is becoming increasingly important. The service industry considers service quality as the basis for competitive advantage (Rashid & Rokade, 2019). Service quality from the customer's perspective is seen as a core component of the service promise that cannot be compromised. Parasuraman et al. (1988) explained the concept of service quality as the difference between customer expectations and perceived service performance. Specifically, service quality explains that the service delivered must meet customer needs and expectations. Service quality is not seen from the perspective of the organizer or service provider, but based on customer perception, because customers consume and know the services offered, they must evaluate and determine the quality of the service.

Previous studies have revealed that ignoring service quality can result in decreased visitors (Abdulla et al. 2019). This is also supported by research by An et al. (2019) and Khoo (2020) which state that service quality has a positive and significant effect on revisit intention. Therefore, the service quality aspect of an organization must be managed effectively for the longevity and profitability of any business. Measurement of service quality variables (Sitepu & Rismawati, 2021) with five indicators, namely: tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurances, and empathy.

Health Consciousness

Gabor & Oltean (2019) refer to health consciousness as an individual's behavior in consuming food and doing physical activities, such as consuming healthy foods and exercising. Damijanac (2019) defines health consciousness as an activity related to measuring the level of health awareness. Arpasi (2018) found that an important factor in deciding to do wellness tourism activities is health awareness.

Furthermore, Hao & Chenyue (2021) stated that health awareness affects consumption intentions. In addition, consumer behavior changes when their health awareness preferences change according to changes in their lives. If consumers are willing to pay or are willing to change their consumption, it can be indicated that they feel some benefits. According to Anannukul & Yoopetch (2022), health consciousness in tourists is as follows: aware of my health, usually do fitness activities, and are active to improve the quality of my health.

Perceived Value

A theoretical and empirical construct, perceived value has received increasing attention not only in marketing, but also in tourism and hospitality literature. The roots of the concept of perceived value come from consumer behavior theory and is defined as 'a consumer's overall assessment of the usefulness of a product or service based on perceptions of what is received and what is given' (Zeithaml, 1988). Perceived value is a consumer's overall assessment of monetary and nonmonetary considerations for a product or service based on perceptions of what is received and what is given. Perceived value is also considered as "a consumer's overall assessment of the usefulness of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given" (Zeithaml, 1988).

Customer perceived value has been established as a strong behavioral predictor of intention in many consumer behavior and revisit intentions of tourists in tourism studies (Damanik & Yusuf, 2022; Mursid & Anoraga, 2021). Likewise, Allameh et al. (2015), in their study concluded that perceived value has a strong influence on tourists' revisit intentions to sports tourism destinations. This implies that when tourists perceive a higher value from a destination they visit, they tend to develop an intention to revisit. Keshavarz & Jamshidi's (2018) study measured perceived value from three different perspectives: emotive, cognitive, and social/self-concept to examine the relationship between service quality, perceived value, satisfaction, and hotel guest loyalty. The indicators used to measure the perceived value variable according to An et al. (2019) include: the services offered are valuable, the prices offered are appropriate and it will be more beneficial to use the service.

Revisit Intention

According to Amaro (2020), it explains that revisit intention is the possibility of tourists to repeat activities or revisit a destination. Revisit intention or repurchase intention can be interpreted as the customer's desire to carry out certain activities related to future purchases. Lee (2017), explains that the definition of repurchase intention is customer behavior that responds positively to a company's products and intends to repurchase and reintroduce the company's products. Chen et al. (2020) argue that revisit intention refers to the probability or willingness of consumers who have completed an initial visit and continue to visit the same place in the future.

Revisit intention also means the consumer's decision to revisit the same destination (Sukaatmadja et al., 2022; Liestiandre et al., 2024), while according to Primananda et al. (2022) the intention to revisit a tourism destination is a person's readiness or willingness to make repeat visits to the same destination and provides the most accurate prediction of their decision to revisit. Indicators of revisit intention according to Chen et al. (2020) are will revisit, first choice of destination, and strong intention.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Judging from the nature of the problem, this research is a type of descriptive qualitative research. This means that this research provides an overview of respondents' perceptions of Service Quality, Health Consciousness, Perceived Value, and Revisit Intention. The research was conducted on tourists who had visited ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali. Data collection through questionnaires distributed offline and online. The data collected from 30 respondents were tested for validity and reliability. The results of the validity and reliability tests showed that the correlation values of all indicators were all above 0.30; and the results of the reliability test showed that the Cronbach's Alpha values of all variables were above 0.6.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test Results

The validity and reliability testing of the instrument was carried out using Pearson Correlation and Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. As previously stated, the research instrument is said to be valid if the Pearson Product Moment correlation value $r \geq 0.30$ and reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value ≥ 0.60 . The test results on thirty (30) respondents have been carried out and provided the following results.

Table 1: Results of Instrument Validity and Reliability Testing

Variable	Item	Correlation r	Cronbach's Alpha
Service quality (X1)	X1		0,891
	X1.1	0,826	
	X1.2	0,783	
	X1.3	0,851	
	X1.4	0,884	
	X1.5	0,894	
Health consciousness (X2)	X2		0,932
	X2.1	0,936	
	X2.2	0,954	
	X2.3	0,931	
Perceived Value (Y1)	Y1		0,872
	Y1.1	0,894	
	Y1.2	0,969	
	Y1.3	0,819	
Revisit Intention (Y2)	Y2		0,957
	Y2.1	0,951	
	Y2.2	0,965	
	Y2.3	0,977	

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Description of Respondent Characteristics

The characteristics of respondents in this study are seen from gender, age, status, last education, occupation, and income. The composition of the characteristics of the research respondents is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

No	Variable	Classification	Total (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Man	52	37,14
		Woman	88	62,86
		Total	140	100,00
2	Age	20 - 30	5	3,57
		>30 - 40	10	7,14
		>40 - 50	68	48,57
		>50 - 60	45	32,14
		>60	12	8,58
		Total	140	100,00
3	Education Background	High School	55	39,29
		Diploma	13	9,29
		Bachelor's Degree	50	35,71
		Postgraduate	22	15,71
		Total	140	100,00
5	Types of tourists	Domestic tourists	85	60,71
		Foreign tourists	55	39,29
		Total	140	100,00
6	Length of visit	1 – 3 days	70	50,00
		> 3 – 5 days	35	25,00
		>5 days	35	25,00
		Total	140	100,00

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Table 2 provides an overview of the profile of 140 respondents presented in general with several characteristics including gender, age, education, type of tourist, and duration of travel. The characteristics of the respondents in this study can be described as follows. There are more female respondents than male respondents, namely 88 women and 52 male respondents. The age range is from 20 to 65 years, with the following distribution. Those aged 20-30 years are 5 people, aged > 30 - 40 years are 10 people, those aged > 40 - 50 years are 68 people, aged > 50 - 60 years are 45 people, and those aged > 60 years are 12 people. The level of education of the respondents is as follows: 55 high school students, 13 diploma students, 50 undergraduate students, and 22 postgraduate students. Types of tourists, namely 85 domestic tourists and 55 foreign tourists. Furthermore, for the duration of traveling or vacationing in Bali, the duration of vacation for 1-3 days was 70 people, > 3-5 days was 35 people, and > 5 days was 35 people.

Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The frequency distribution was obtained from the respondents' answer scores. The interpretation of the item scores in the research variables can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Measurement Criteria Description of Research Variables

No.	Measurement Scale	Service quality	Health consciousness, perceived value, revisit intention
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very bad	Very low
2	>1.80 – 2.60	Not Good	Low
3	>2.60 – 3.40	Quite good	Quite high
4	>3.40 – 4.20	Good	High
5	>4.20 – 5.00	Very good	Very high

Source: Ghozali (2014)

Description of the descriptive statistical analysis of each variable, as follows:

Service quality (X1)

The service quality variable is one of the variables related to the variable of revisit intention. This research variable measures the quality of service owned by ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali with a quantitative approach, namely based on the responses of respondents (tourists who have visited Bali) to the service quality indicators owned by ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali, namely the indicators: Ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali that have been visited are clean (X1.1); Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide reliable information (X1.2); Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are responsive in serving (X1.3); Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide security guarantees (X1.4); Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali care about tourists (X1.5). Respondents' perceptions of the service quality variable can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of Descriptive Analysis of Service Quality Variables (X1)

Indicator	Answer Score					Mean	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5		
Ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali that have been visited are clean (X1.1)	0	0	7	56	77	4.50	Very good
Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide reliable information (X1.2)	0	0	7	51	82	4.54	Very good
Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are responsive in serving (X1.3)	0	0	16	58	66	4.36	Very good
Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide security guarantees (X1.4)	0	1	12	65	62	4.34	Very good
Staff at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali care about tourists (X1.5)	0	7	23	61	49	4.09	Good
Service Quality (X1)						4.36	Very good

Source: processed primary data, 2024

The quality of service owned by the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali is shown by Bali as a clean ethnowellness tourism destination in Bali that has been visited (X1.1); The staff at the ethnowellness tourism destination in Bali are able to provide reliable information (X1.2); The staff at the ethnowellness tourism destination in Bali are responsive in serving (X1.3); The staff at the ethnowellness tourism destination in Bali are able to provide security guarantees (X1.4); The staff at the ethnowellness tourism destination in Bali care about tourists (X1.5). Based on Table 4, it can be seen that out of 140 respondents studied, in general the perception of tourists who have visited ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali regarding the service quality variable indicator has an average score of 4.36 and it is stated that the quality of service owned can be said to be very good. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand the quality of ethnowellness tourism destination services in Bali as indicated by the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali that have been visited are clean, the staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide reliable information, the staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are responsive in serving, the staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali are able to provide security guarantees, the staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali care about tourists. Of the five indicators of service quality, it turns out that the indicator of Staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali is able to provide reliable information (X1.2) shows the highest mean value, which is 4.54, while the lowest is Staff at the ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali care about tourists (X1.5) with a mean value of 4.09. This illustrates that according to tourists, the quality of ethnowellness tourism destination services in Bali needs to increase concern for tourists.

Health consciousness (X2)

Measurement of Health consciousness of tourists who have visited Bali, referring to the research of Anannukul & Yoopetch (2022), which consists of: Health conscious (X2.1); Accustomed to doing fitness activities (X2.2), and Active to improve health quality (X2.3). Based on Table 5, it can be seen that of the 140 respondents studied, in general, the perception of tourists who have visited ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali regarding the Health consciousness variable indicator of tourists is in the very high category with an average score of 4.25. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand that Health consciousness of tourists is indicated by being health conscious, accustomed to doing fitness activities, and active to improve health quality.

Table 5: Results of Descriptive Analysis of Health Consciousness Variable (X2)

Indicator	Answer Score					Mean	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5		
Health conscious (X2.1)	0	1	16	72	51	4.24	Very high
Usually doing fitness activities (X2.2)	0	1	17	68	54	4.25	Very high
Active to improve health quality (X2.3)	0	0	14	73	53	4.28	Very high
Health consciousness						4.25	Very high

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Of the three health consciousness indicators of tourists, it turns out that the active indicator value to improve health quality (X2.3), shows the highest mean value, which is 4.28 while the lowest is the health awareness indicator (X2.1), which is 4.24. This illustrates that tourists who have visited ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali indicate that they are very aware of health.

Perceived value (Y1)

Measurement of the perceived value variable for ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali consists of: Carrying out valuable ethnowellness tourism activities (Y1.1); The price range of services offered at ethnowellness tourism destinations is in accordance with the quality of service (Y1.2); Feeling more useful if doing ethnowellness tourism (Y1.3). Based on Table 6, it can be seen that of the 140 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of tourists who have visited ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali regarding the perceived value variable indicator is in the very high category with an average score of 4.23. This illustrates a condition where respondents understand the perceived value felt by tourists when visiting ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali, as indicated by the indicator.

Table 6: Results of Descriptive Analysis of Perceived Value Variable (Y1)

Indicator	Answer Score					Mean	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5		
Conducting ethnowellness tourism activities is valuable (Y1.1)	0	1	21	72	46	4.16	High
The price range of services offered at ethnowellness tourism destinations is in accordance with the quality of service (Y1.2)	0	0	15	74	51	4.26	Very high
Feeling more beneficial if doing ethnowellness tourism (Y1.3)	0	1	13	75	51	4.26	Very high
Perceived Value (Y1)						4.23	Very high

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Of the three indicators of perceived value variables, it turns out that the value of the indicator of the price range of services offered at ethnowellness tourism destinations is in accordance with the quality of service (Y1.2) and feeling more beneficial if doing ethnowellness tourism (Y1.3) shows the highest mean value, which is 4.26 while the lowest mean value is the indicator of carrying out valuable ethnowellness tourism activities (Y1.1), which is 4.16. This illustrates that tourists feel perceived value when visiting ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali and the indicator of carrying out valuable ethnowellness tourism activities needs to be improved.

Intention to Revisit (Y2)

Measurement of the intention to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali consists of: in the future wanting to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali (Y2.1); making the first choice to carry out ethnowellness tourism activities on vacation (Y2.2), having a strong intention to visit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali (Y2.3). Based on Table 7, it can be seen that from the 140 respondents studied, it turns out that in general the perception of tourists who have been to Bali regarding the variable indicator of intention to revisit is in the very high category with an average score of 4.34. This illustrates a condition that respondents understand the intention to revisit Bali which is indicated by the indicators of wanting to revisit Bali in the future, making Bali their first choice for traveling, wanting to vacation in Bali repeatedly, and wanting to repeat returning to Bali.

Table 7: Results of Descriptive Analysis of Revisit Intention Variable (Y2)

Indicator	Answer Score					Mean	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4	5		
In the future, want to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali (Y2.1)	0	1	12	68	59	4.32	Very high
Make it the first choice to do ethnowellness tourism activities while on vacation (Y2.2)	0	0	15	60	65	4.36	Very high
Have a strong intention to visit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali (Y2.3)	0	0	14	65	61	4.34	Very high
Revisit Intention (Y2)						4.34	Very high

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Of the three indicators of revisit intention, it turns out that the indicator value of Making the first choice to do ethnowellness tourism activities on vacation (Y2.2) shows the highest mean value, which is 4.36, while the lowest is the indicator in the future wanting to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali (Y2.1), which is 4.32. This illustrates that the intention to revisit Bali is very high, and the indicator in the future wanting to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali needs to be continuously improved.

5. RESEARCH CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The results of the descriptive analysis show that the quality of service at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali is included in the very good category, this means that the quality of service provided to tourists must be maintained. For health consciousness owned by tourists is included in the very high category. This means that tourists who visit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali have a very high awareness of health. Furthermore, the perceived value felt by tourists after enjoying the services at ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali is also categorized as very high, and this means that the perceived value given to tourists needs to be maintained in order to have a positive impact on increasing the intention to revisit. This study describes the quality of service, health consciousness, perceived value, and intention to revisit, so that the results of the study can be used as a basis for developing a strategy model to increase the intention to revisit ethnowellness tourism destinations in Bali.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks are expressed to LPPM Unud and the tourists who have been willing to be respondents, so that the implementation of this Udayana Leading Research can run well, smoothly, and successfully.

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